

Table S2. Mean Fluorescence Intensity of Bacteria phagocytosed by monocytes or neutrophils of non-pregnant women, pregnant women, and neonates.

Phagocytosis	Hours	0			24		
		NP	P	N	NP	P	N
MFI pHrodo <i>E. coli</i> in monocytes							
WB alone		1294	3589	5012	3141	4884	2536
+IVIg		1294	3589	5012	2615	4885	3091
+LPS		1294	3589	5012	2635	4149	1570
+IVIg + LPS		1294	3589	5012	3025	5360	1962
MFI pHrodo <i>E. coli</i> in neutrophils							
WB alone		2039	3890	5569	3429	4922	2969
+IVIg		2039	3890	5569	3440	7208	5735
+LPS		2039	3890	5569	3453	5515	2519
+IVIg + LPS		2039	3890	5569	3347	5822	2944

Data show the mean of MFI in monocytes or neutrophils. WB: Whole Blood. Non-pregnant (NP, n=5), Pregnant (P, n=3) and Newborns (N, n=5). Differences between times were calculated using a bootstarp RM ANOVA.

Univariate Analysis of Variance-Phagocytosis

Notes

Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\ruthm\OneDrive\Escritorio\Doc. Cerbulo\ART Fc\Analisis anova robusta\Fcgamma.sav
	Active Dataset	ConjuntoDatos2
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	839
	Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data for all variables in the model.

Syntax

```
UNIANOVA Value BY  
Treatment Group  
  
/METHOD=SSTYPE(3)  
  
/INTERCEPT=INCLUDE  
  
/POSTHOC=Treatment  
Group(TUKEY)  
  
/PLOT=PROFILE(Group*Tre  
atment) TYPE=BAR  
ERRORBAR=CI  
MEANREFERENCE=NO  
  
/EMMEANS=TABLES(OVER  
ALL)  
  
/EMMEANS=TABLES(Treatm  
ent)  
  
/EMMEANS=TABLES(Group)  
  
/EMMEANS=TABLES(Group*  
Treatment)  
  
/PRINT HOMOGENEITY  
  
/CRITERIA=ALPHA(.05)  
  
/DESIGN=Treatment Group  
Group*Treatment.
```

Resources

Processor Time

00:00:00.27

Elapsed Time

00:00:00.23

Between-Subjects Factors

		N
Treatment	Mono IVIg %	18
	Mono IVIg MFI	18
	Mono LPS %	18
	Mono LPS+IVIg %	18
	Mono LPS+IVIg MFI	18
	Mono SE %	18
	Mono SE MFI	18
	Neutro IVIg %	18
	Neutro IVIg MFI	18
	Neutro LPS %	18
	Neutro LPS MFI	18
	Neutro LPS+IVIg %	18
	Neutro LPS+IVIg MFI	18
	Neutro SE %	18
	Neutro SE MFI	18

Group	0N	45
	0NP	45
	0P	45
	24N	45
	24NP	45
	24P	45

Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances^{a,b}

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Value	Based on Mean	1.627	35	234	.019
	Based on Median	1.027	35	234	.433
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	1.027	35	107.547	.442
	Based on trimmed mean	1.448	35	234	.058

Tests the null hypothesis that the error variance of the dependent variable is equal across groups.^{a,b}

a. Dependent variable: Value

b. Design: Intercept + Treatment + Group + Treatment * Group

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Value

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1184871625.694 ^a	89	13313164.334	3.829	.000
Intercept	874941017.683	1	874941017.683	251.613	.000
Treatment	941742788.194	14	67267342.014	19.345	.000
Group	102350734.002	5	20470146.800	5.887	.000
Treatment * Group	140778103.497	70	2011115.764	.578	.995
Error	625918675.934	180	3477325.977		
Total	2685731319.310	270			
Corrected Total	1810790301.628	269			

a. R Squared = .654 (Adjusted R Squared = .483)

Estimated Marginal Means

1. Grand Mean

Dependent Variable: Value

Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval
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		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1800.145	113.486	1576.212	2024.078

2. Treatment

Dependent Variable: Value

Treatment	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Mono IVlg %	76.418	439.528	-790.872	943.708
Mono IVlg MFI	3414.156	439.528	2546.866	4281.446
Mono LPS %	76.769	439.528	-790.521	944.059
Mono LPS+IVlg %	76.186	439.528	-791.104	943.476
Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	3373.541	439.528	2506.251	4240.831
Mono SE %	76.803	439.528	-790.487	944.093
Mono SE MFI	3409.329	439.528	2542.039	4276.619
Neutro IVlg %	69.836	439.528	-797.454	937.126
Neutro IVlg MFI	4646.987	439.528	3779.697	5514.277
Neutro LPS %	71.675	439.528	-795.615	938.965
Neutro LPS MFI	3831.122	439.528	2963.832	4698.412

Neutro LPS+IVlg %	71.091	439.528	-796.199	938.381
Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	3935.361	439.528	3068.071	4802.651
Neutro SE %	69.787	439.528	-797.503	937.077
Neutro SE MFI	3803.116	439.528	2935.826	4670.406

3. Group

Dependent Variable: Value

Group	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
0N	2516.558	277.982	1968.036	3065.081
0NP	850.047	277.982	301.525	1398.569
0P	1805.329	277.982	1256.807	2353.851
24N	1464.991	277.982	916.469	2013.513
24NP	1540.069	277.982	991.547	2088.592
24P	2623.876	277.982	2075.353	3172.398

4. Group * Treatment

Dependent Variable: Value

Group	Treatment	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
ON	Mono IVlg %	74.500	1076.619	-2049.918	2198.918
	Mono IVlg MFI	5011.583	1076.619	2887.165	7136.001
	Mono LPS %	74.500	1076.619	-2049.918	2198.918
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	74.500	1076.619	-2049.918	2198.918
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	5011.583	1076.619	2887.165	7136.001
	Mono SE %	74.500	1076.619	-2049.918	2198.918
	Mono SE MFI	5011.583	1076.619	2887.165	7136.001
	Neutro IVlg %	34.920	1076.619	-2089.498	2159.338
	Neutro IVlg MFI	5568.987	1076.619	3444.569	7693.405
	Neutro LPS %	34.920	1076.619	-2089.498	2159.338
	Neutro LPS MFI	5568.987	1076.619	3444.569	7693.405
	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	34.920	1076.619	-2089.498	2159.338
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	5568.987	1076.619	3444.569	7693.405
	Neutro SE %	34.920	1076.619	-2089.498	2159.338
	Neutro SE MFI	5568.987	1076.619	3444.569	7693.405
	ONP	Mono IVlg %	90.853	1076.619	-2033.565
Mono IVlg MFI		1294.333	1076.619	-830.085	3418.751

	Mono LPS %	90.853	1076.619	-2033.565	2215.271
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	90.853	1076.619	-2033.565	2215.271
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	1294.333	1076.619	-830.085	3418.751
	Mono SE %	90.853	1076.619	-2033.565	2215.271
	Mono SE MFI	1294.333	1076.619	-830.085	3418.751
	Neutro IVlg %	86.683	1076.619	-2037.735	2211.101
	Neutro IVlg MFI	2039.390	1076.619	-85.028	4163.808
	Neutro LPS %	86.683	1076.619	-2037.735	2211.101
	Neutro LPS MFI	2039.390	1076.619	-85.028	4163.808
	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	86.683	1076.619	-2037.735	2211.101
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	2039.390	1076.619	-85.028	4163.808
	Neutro SE %	86.683	1076.619	-2037.735	2211.101
	Neutro SE MFI	2039.390	1076.619	-85.028	4163.808
OP	Mono IVlg %	93.817	1076.619	-2030.601	2218.235
	Mono IVlg MFI	3588.637	1076.619	1464.219	5713.055
	Mono LPS %	93.817	1076.619	-2030.601	2218.235
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	93.817	1076.619	-2030.601	2218.235
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	3588.637	1076.619	1464.219	5713.055
	Mono SE %	93.817	1076.619	-2030.601	2218.235

	Mono SE MFI	3588.637	1076.619	1464.219	5713.055
	Neutro IVlg %	94.217	1076.619	-2030.201	2218.635
	Neutro IVlg MFI	3890.473	1076.619	1766.055	6014.891
	Neutro LPS %	94.217	1076.619	-2030.201	2218.635
	Neutro LPS MFI	3890.473	1076.619	1766.055	6014.891
	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	94.217	1076.619	-2030.201	2218.635
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	3890.473	1076.619	1766.055	6014.891
	Neutro SE %	94.217	1076.619	-2030.201	2218.635
	Neutro SE MFI	3890.473	1076.619	1766.055	6014.891
24N	Mono IVlg %	21.820	1076.619	-2102.598	2146.238
	Mono IVlg MFI	3090.750	1076.619	966.332	5215.168
	Mono LPS %	20.100	1076.619	-2104.318	2144.518
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	19.323	1076.619	-2105.095	2143.741
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	1962.170	1076.619	-162.248	4086.588
	Mono SE %	18.747	1076.619	-2105.671	2143.165
	Mono SE MFI	2535.960	1076.619	411.542	4660.378
	Neutro IVlg %	44.283	1076.619	-2080.135	2168.701
	Neutro IVlg MFI	5735.050	1076.619	3610.632	7859.468
	Neutro LPS %	31.677	1076.619	-2092.741	2156.095

	Neutro LPS MFI	2519.333	1076.619	394.915	4643.751
	Neutro LPS+IVIg %	36.333	1076.619	-2088.085	2160.751
	Neutro LPS+IVIg MFI	2943.623	1076.619	819.205	5068.041
	Neutro SE %	26.440	1076.619	-2097.978	2150.858
	Neutro SE MFI	2969.253	1076.619	844.835	5093.671
24NP	Mono IVIg %	82.943	1076.619	-2041.475	2207.361
	Mono IVIg MFI	2614.627	1076.619	490.209	4739.045
	Mono LPS %	86.127	1076.619	-2038.291	2210.545
	Mono LPS+IVIg %	82.890	1076.619	-2041.528	2207.308
	Mono LPS+IVIg MFI	3024.747	1076.619	900.329	5149.165
	Mono SE %	88.040	1076.619	-2036.378	2212.458
	Mono SE MFI	3141.463	1076.619	1017.045	5265.881
	Neutro IVIg %	65.493	1076.619	-2058.925	2189.911
	Neutro IVIg MFI	3440.033	1076.619	1315.615	5564.451
	Neutro LPS %	84.803	1076.619	-2039.615	2209.221
	Neutro LPS MFI	3453.247	1076.619	1328.829	5577.665
	Neutro LPS+IVIg %	78.223	1076.619	-2046.195	2202.641
	Neutro LPS+IVIg MFI	3347.333	1076.619	1222.915	5471.751
	Neutro SE %	82.033	1076.619	-2042.385	2206.451

	Neutro SE MFI	3429.037	1076.619	1304.619	5553.455
24P	Mono IVlg %	94.573	1076.619	-2029.845	2218.991
	Mono IVlg MFI	4885.007	1076.619	2760.589	7009.425
	Mono LPS %	95.220	1076.619	-2029.198	2219.638
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	95.733	1076.619	-2028.685	2220.151
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	5359.773	1076.619	3235.355	7484.191
	Mono SE %	94.863	1076.619	-2029.555	2219.281
	Mono SE MFI	4884.000	1076.619	2759.582	7008.418
	Neutro IVlg %	93.417	1076.619	-2031.001	2217.835
	Neutro IVlg MFI	7207.990	1076.619	5083.572	9332.408
	Neutro LPS %	97.750	1076.619	-2026.668	2222.168
	Neutro LPS MFI	5515.303	1076.619	3390.885	7639.721
	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	96.167	1076.619	-2028.251	2220.585
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	5822.357	1076.619	3697.939	7946.775
	Neutro SE %	94.427	1076.619	-2029.991	2218.845
	Neutro SE MFI	4921.553	1076.619	2797.135	7045.971

Post Hoc Tests

Treatment

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Value

Tukey HSD

(I) Treatment	(J) Treatment	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Mono IVIg %	Mono IVIg MFI	-3337.74*	621.586	.000	-5475.50	-1199.98
	Mono LPS %	-.35	621.586	1.000	-2138.11	2137.41
	Mono LPS+IVIg %	.23	621.586	1.000	-2137.53	2137.99
	Mono LPS+IVIg MFI	-3297.12*	621.586	.000	-5434.88	-1159.36
	Mono SE %	-.39	621.586	1.000	-2138.14	2137.37
	Mono SE MFI	-3332.91*	621.586	.000	-5470.67	-1195.15
	Neutro IVIg %	6.58	621.586	1.000	-2131.18	2144.34
	Neutro IVIg MFI	-4570.57*	621.586	.000	-6708.33	-2432.81
	Neutro LPS %	4.74	621.586	1.000	-2133.02	2142.50
	Neutro LPS MFI	-3754.70*	621.586	.000	-5892.46	-1616.95
	Neutro LPS+IVIg %	5.33	621.586	1.000	-2132.43	2143.09
	Neutro LPS+IVIg MFI	-3858.94*	621.586	.000	-5996.70	-1721.18

	Neutro SE %	6.63	621.586	1.000	-2131.13	2144.39
	Neutro SE MFI	-3726.70*	621.586	.000	-5864.46	-1588.94
Mono IVIg MFI	Mono IVIg %	3337.74*	621.586	.000	1199.98	5475.50
	Mono LPS %	3337.39*	621.586	.000	1199.63	5475.15
	Mono LPS+IVIg %	3337.97*	621.586	.000	1200.21	5475.73
	Mono LPS+IVIg MFI	40.62	621.586	1.000	-2097.14	2178.37
	Mono SE %	3337.35*	621.586	.000	1199.59	5475.11
	Mono SE MFI	4.83	621.586	1.000	-2132.93	2142.59
	Neutro IVIg %	3344.32*	621.586	.000	1206.56	5482.08
	Neutro IVIg MFI	-1232.83	621.586	.805	-3370.59	904.93
	Neutro LPS %	3342.48*	621.586	.000	1204.72	5480.24
	Neutro LPS MFI	-416.97	621.586	1.000	-2554.73	1720.79
	Neutro LPS+IVIg %	3343.07*	621.586	.000	1205.31	5480.82
	Neutro LPS+IVIg MFI	-521.20	621.586	1.000	-2658.96	1616.55
	Neutro SE %	3344.37*	621.586	.000	1206.61	5482.13
	Neutro SE MFI	-388.96	621.586	1.000	-2526.72	1748.80
	Mono LPS %	Mono IVIg %	.35	621.586	1.000	-2137.41
Mono IVIg MFI		-3337.39*	621.586	.000	-5475.15	-1199.63

	Mono LPS+IVlg %	.58	621.586	1.000	-2137.18	2138.34
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	-3296.77*	621.586	.000	-5434.53	-1159.01
	Mono SE %	-.03	621.586	1.000	-2137.79	2137.73
	Mono SE MFI	-3332.56*	621.586	.000	-5470.32	-1194.80
	Neutro IVlg %	6.93	621.586	1.000	-2130.83	2144.69
	Neutro IVlg MFI	-4570.22*	621.586	.000	-6707.98	-2432.46
	Neutro LPS %	5.09	621.586	1.000	-2132.66	2142.85
	Neutro LPS MFI	-3754.35*	621.586	.000	-5892.11	-1616.59
	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	5.68	621.586	1.000	-2132.08	2143.44
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	-3858.59*	621.586	.000	-5996.35	-1720.83
	Neutro SE %	6.98	621.586	1.000	-2130.78	2144.74
	Neutro SE MFI	-3726.35*	621.586	.000	-5864.11	-1588.59
Mono LPS+IVlg %	Mono IVlg %	-.23	621.586	1.000	-2137.99	2137.53
	Mono IVlg MFI	-3337.97*	621.586	.000	-5475.73	-1200.21
	Mono LPS %	-.58	621.586	1.000	-2138.34	2137.18
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	-3297.35*	621.586	.000	-5435.11	-1159.60
	Mono SE %	-.62	621.586	1.000	-2138.38	2137.14
	Mono SE MFI	-3333.14*	621.586	.000	-5470.90	-1195.38

	Neutro IVlg %	6.35	621.586	1.000	-2131.41	2144.11
	Neutro IVlg MFI	-4570.80*	621.586	.000	-6708.56	-2433.04
	Neutro LPS %	4.51	621.586	1.000	-2133.25	2142.27
	Neutro LPS MFI	-3754.94*	621.586	.000	-5892.70	-1617.18
	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	5.10	621.586	1.000	-2132.66	2142.85
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	-3859.17*	621.586	.000	-5996.93	-1721.42
	Neutro SE %	6.40	621.586	1.000	-2131.36	2144.16
	Neutro SE MFI	-3726.93*	621.586	.000	-5864.69	-1589.17
Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	Mono IVlg %	3297.12*	621.586	.000	1159.36	5434.88
	Mono IVlg MFI	-40.62	621.586	1.000	-2178.37	2097.14
	Mono LPS %	3296.77*	621.586	.000	1159.01	5434.53
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	3297.35*	621.586	.000	1159.60	5435.11
	Mono SE %	3296.74*	621.586	.000	1158.98	5434.50
	Mono SE MFI	-35.79	621.586	1.000	-2173.55	2101.97
	Neutro IVlg %	3303.71*	621.586	.000	1165.95	5441.46
	Neutro IVlg MFI	-1273.45	621.586	.766	-3411.21	864.31
	Neutro LPS %	3301.87*	621.586	.000	1164.11	5439.62
	Neutro LPS MFI	-457.58	621.586	1.000	-2595.34	1680.18

	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	3302.45*	621.586	.000	1164.69	5440.21
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	-561.82	621.586	1.000	-2699.58	1575.94
	Neutro SE %	3303.75*	621.586	.000	1165.99	5441.51
	Neutro SE MFI	-429.58	621.586	1.000	-2567.33	1708.18
Mono SE %	Mono IVlg %	.39	621.586	1.000	-2137.37	2138.14
	Mono IVlg MFI	-3337.35*	621.586	.000	-5475.11	-1199.59
	Mono LPS %	.03	621.586	1.000	-2137.73	2137.79
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	.62	621.586	1.000	-2137.14	2138.38
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	-3296.74*	621.586	.000	-5434.50	-1158.98
	Mono SE MFI	-3332.53*	621.586	.000	-5470.29	-1194.77
	Neutro IVlg %	6.97	621.586	1.000	-2130.79	2144.73
	Neutro IVlg MFI	-4570.18*	621.586	.000	-6707.94	-2432.42
	Neutro LPS %	5.13	621.586	1.000	-2132.63	2142.89
	Neutro LPS MFI	-3754.32*	621.586	.000	-5892.08	-1616.56
	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	5.71	621.586	1.000	-2132.05	2143.47
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	-3858.56*	621.586	.000	-5996.32	-1720.80
	Neutro SE %	7.02	621.586	1.000	-2130.74	2144.78
	Neutro SE MFI	-3726.31*	621.586	.000	-5864.07	-1588.55

Mono SE MFI	Mono IVIg %	3332.91*	621.586	.000	1195.15	5470.67
	Mono IVIg MFI	-4.83	621.586	1.000	-2142.59	2132.93
	Mono LPS %	3332.56*	621.586	.000	1194.80	5470.32
	Mono LPS+IVIg %	3333.14*	621.586	.000	1195.38	5470.90
	Mono LPS+IVIg MFI	35.79	621.586	1.000	-2101.97	2173.55
	Mono SE %	3332.53*	621.586	.000	1194.77	5470.29
	Neutro IVIg %	3339.49*	621.586	.000	1201.73	5477.25
	Neutro IVIg MFI	-1237.66	621.586	.801	-3375.42	900.10
	Neutro LPS %	3337.65*	621.586	.000	1199.90	5475.41
	Neutro LPS MFI	-421.79	621.586	1.000	-2559.55	1715.97
	Neutro LPS+IVIg %	3338.24*	621.586	.000	1200.48	5476.00
	Neutro LPS+IVIg MFI	-526.03	621.586	1.000	-2663.79	1611.73
	Neutro SE %	3339.54*	621.586	.000	1201.78	5477.30
	Neutro SE MFI	-393.79	621.586	1.000	-2531.55	1743.97
Neutro IVIg %	Mono IVIg %	-6.58	621.586	1.000	-2144.34	2131.18
	Mono IVIg MFI	-3344.32*	621.586	.000	-5482.08	-1206.56
	Mono LPS %	-6.93	621.586	1.000	-2144.69	2130.83
	Mono LPS+IVIg %	-6.35	621.586	1.000	-2144.11	2131.41

	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	-3303.71*	621.586	.000	-5441.46	-1165.95
	Mono SE %	-6.97	621.586	1.000	-2144.73	2130.79
	Mono SE MFI	-3339.49*	621.586	.000	-5477.25	-1201.73
	Neutro IVlg MFI	-4577.15*	621.586	.000	-6714.91	-2439.39
	Neutro LPS %	-1.84	621.586	1.000	-2139.60	2135.92
	Neutro LPS MFI	-3761.29*	621.586	.000	-5899.05	-1623.53
	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	-1.26	621.586	1.000	-2139.01	2136.50
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	-3865.52*	621.586	.000	-6003.28	-1727.77
	Neutro SE %	.05	621.586	1.000	-2137.71	2137.81
	Neutro SE MFI	-3733.28*	621.586	.000	-5871.04	-1595.52
Neutro IVlg MFI	Mono IVlg %	4570.57*	621.586	.000	2432.81	6708.33
	Mono IVlg MFI	1232.83	621.586	.805	-904.93	3370.59
	Mono LPS %	4570.22*	621.586	.000	2432.46	6707.98
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	4570.80*	621.586	.000	2433.04	6708.56
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	1273.45	621.586	.766	-864.31	3411.21
	Mono SE %	4570.18*	621.586	.000	2432.42	6707.94
	Mono SE MFI	1237.66	621.586	.801	-900.10	3375.42
	Neutro IVlg %	4577.15*	621.586	.000	2439.39	6714.91

	Neutro LPS %	4575.31*	621.586	.000	2437.55	6713.07
	Neutro LPS MFI	815.86	621.586	.993	-1321.89	2953.62
	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	4575.90*	621.586	.000	2438.14	6713.66
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	711.63	621.586	.998	-1426.13	2849.39
	Neutro SE %	4577.20*	621.586	.000	2439.44	6714.96
	Neutro SE MFI	843.87	621.586	.990	-1293.89	2981.63
Neutro LPS %	Mono IVlg %	-4.74	621.586	1.000	-2142.50	2133.02
	Mono IVlg MFI	-3342.48*	621.586	.000	-5480.24	-1204.72
	Mono LPS %	-5.09	621.586	1.000	-2142.85	2132.66
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	-4.51	621.586	1.000	-2142.27	2133.25
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	-3301.87*	621.586	.000	-5439.62	-1164.11
	Mono SE %	-5.13	621.586	1.000	-2142.89	2132.63
	Mono SE MFI	-3337.65*	621.586	.000	-5475.41	-1199.90
	Neutro IVlg %	1.84	621.586	1.000	-2135.92	2139.60
	Neutro IVlg MFI	-4575.31*	621.586	.000	-6713.07	-2437.55
	Neutro LPS MFI	-3759.45*	621.586	.000	-5897.21	-1621.69
	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	.58	621.586	1.000	-2137.17	2138.34
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	-3863.69*	621.586	.000	-6001.44	-1725.93

	Neutro SE %	1.89	621.586	1.000	-2135.87	2139.65
	Neutro SE MFI	-3731.44*	621.586	.000	-5869.20	-1593.68
Neutro LPS MFI	Mono IVIg %	3754.70*	621.586	.000	1616.95	5892.46
	Mono IVIg MFI	416.97	621.586	1.000	-1720.79	2554.73
	Mono LPS %	3754.35*	621.586	.000	1616.59	5892.11
	Mono LPS+IVIg %	3754.94*	621.586	.000	1617.18	5892.70
	Mono LPS+IVIg MFI	457.58	621.586	1.000	-1680.18	2595.34
	Mono SE %	3754.32*	621.586	.000	1616.56	5892.08
	Mono SE MFI	421.79	621.586	1.000	-1715.97	2559.55
	Neutro IVIg %	3761.29*	621.586	.000	1623.53	5899.05
	Neutro IVIg MFI	-815.86	621.586	.993	-2953.62	1321.89
	Neutro LPS %	3759.45*	621.586	.000	1621.69	5897.21
	Neutro LPS+IVIg %	3760.03*	621.586	.000	1622.27	5897.79
	Neutro LPS+IVIg MFI	-104.24	621.586	1.000	-2242.00	2033.52
	Neutro SE %	3761.34*	621.586	.000	1623.58	5899.09
	Neutro SE MFI	28.01	621.586	1.000	-2109.75	2165.77
Neutro LPS+IVIg %	Mono IVIg %	-5.33	621.586	1.000	-2143.09	2132.43
	Mono IVIg MFI	-3343.07*	621.586	.000	-5480.82	-1205.31

	Mono LPS %	-5.68	621.586	1.000	-2143.44	2132.08
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	-5.10	621.586	1.000	-2142.85	2132.66
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	-3302.45*	621.586	.000	-5440.21	-1164.69
	Mono SE %	-5.71	621.586	1.000	-2143.47	2132.05
	Mono SE MFI	-3338.24*	621.586	.000	-5476.00	-1200.48
	Neutro IVlg %	1.26	621.586	1.000	-2136.50	2139.01
	Neutro IVlg MFI	-4575.90*	621.586	.000	-6713.66	-2438.14
	Neutro LPS %	-.58	621.586	1.000	-2138.34	2137.17
	Neutro LPS MFI	-3760.03*	621.586	.000	-5897.79	-1622.27
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	-3864.27*	621.586	.000	-6002.03	-1726.51
	Neutro SE %	1.30	621.586	1.000	-2136.46	2139.06
	Neutro SE MFI	-3732.03*	621.586	.000	-5869.78	-1594.27
Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	Mono IVlg %	3858.94*	621.586	.000	1721.18	5996.70
	Mono IVlg MFI	521.20	621.586	1.000	-1616.55	2658.96
	Mono LPS %	3858.59*	621.586	.000	1720.83	5996.35
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	3859.17*	621.586	.000	1721.42	5996.93
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	561.82	621.586	1.000	-1575.94	2699.58
	Mono SE %	3858.56*	621.586	.000	1720.80	5996.32

	Mono SE MFI	526.03	621.586	1.000	-1611.73	2663.79
	Neutro IVIg %	3865.52*	621.586	.000	1727.77	6003.28
	Neutro IVIg MFI	-711.63	621.586	.998	-2849.39	1426.13
	Neutro LPS %	3863.69*	621.586	.000	1725.93	6001.44
	Neutro LPS MFI	104.24	621.586	1.000	-2033.52	2242.00
	Neutro LPS+IVIg %	3864.27*	621.586	.000	1726.51	6002.03
	Neutro SE %	3865.57*	621.586	.000	1727.81	6003.33
	Neutro SE MFI	132.24	621.586	1.000	-2005.51	2270.00
Neutro SE %	Mono IVIg %	-6.63	621.586	1.000	-2144.39	2131.13
	Mono IVIg MFI	-3344.37*	621.586	.000	-5482.13	-1206.61
	Mono LPS %	-6.98	621.586	1.000	-2144.74	2130.78
	Mono LPS+IVIg %	-6.40	621.586	1.000	-2144.16	2131.36
	Mono LPS+IVIg MFI	-3303.75*	621.586	.000	-5441.51	-1165.99
	Mono SE %	-7.02	621.586	1.000	-2144.78	2130.74
	Mono SE MFI	-3339.54*	621.586	.000	-5477.30	-1201.78
	Neutro IVIg %	-.05	621.586	1.000	-2137.81	2137.71
	Neutro IVIg MFI	-4577.20*	621.586	.000	-6714.96	-2439.44
	Neutro LPS %	-1.89	621.586	1.000	-2139.65	2135.87
	Neutro LPS MFI	-3761.34*	621.586	.000	-5899.09	-1623.58

	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	-1.30	621.586	1.000	-2139.06	2136.46
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	-3865.57*	621.586	.000	-6003.33	-1727.81
	Neutro SE MFI	-3733.33*	621.586	.000	-5871.09	-1595.57
Neutro SE MFI	Mono IVlg %	3726.70*	621.586	.000	1588.94	5864.46
	Mono IVlg MFI	388.96	621.586	1.000	-1748.80	2526.72
	Mono LPS %	3726.35*	621.586	.000	1588.59	5864.11
	Mono LPS+IVlg %	3726.93*	621.586	.000	1589.17	5864.69
	Mono LPS+IVlg MFI	429.58	621.586	1.000	-1708.18	2567.33
	Mono SE %	3726.31*	621.586	.000	1588.55	5864.07
	Mono SE MFI	393.79	621.586	1.000	-1743.97	2531.55
	Neutro IVlg %	3733.28*	621.586	.000	1595.52	5871.04
	Neutro IVlg MFI	-843.87	621.586	.990	-2981.63	1293.89
	Neutro LPS %	3731.44*	621.586	.000	1593.68	5869.20
	Neutro LPS MFI	-28.01	621.586	1.000	-2165.77	2109.75
	Neutro LPS+IVlg %	3732.03*	621.586	.000	1594.27	5869.78
	Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	-132.24	621.586	1.000	-2270.00	2005.51
	Neutro SE %	3733.33*	621.586	.000	1595.57	5871.09

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 3477325.977.

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

Homogeneous Subsets

Value

Tukey HSD^{a,b}

Treatment	N	Subset	
		1	2
Neutro SE %	18	69.79	
Neutro IVIg %	18	69.84	
Neutro LPS+IVIg %	18	71.09	
Neutro LPS %	18	71.68	
Mono LPS+IVIg %	18	76.19	
Mono IVIg %	18	76.42	
Mono LPS %	18	76.77	
Mono SE %	18	76.80	
Mono LPS+IVIg MFI	18		3373.54
Mono SE MFI	18		3409.33
Mono IVIg MFI	18		3414.16

Neutro SE MFI	18		3803.12
Neutro LPS MFI	18		3831.12
Neutro LPS+IVlg MFI	18		3935.36
Neutro IVlg MFI	18		4646.99
Sig.		1.000	.766

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 3477325.977.

a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 18.000.

b. Alpha = .05.

Group

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Value

Tukey HSD

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
0N	0NP	1666.51*	393.126	.001	534.05	2798.98
	0P	711.23	393.126	.462	-421.24	1843.69

	24N	1051.57	393.126	.085	-80.90	2184.03
	24NP	976.49	393.126	.134	-155.98	2108.95
	24P	-107.32	393.126	1.000	-1239.78	1025.15
0NP	0N	-1666.51*	393.126	.001	-2798.98	-534.05
	0P	-955.28	393.126	.152	-2087.75	177.18
	24N	-614.94	393.126	.623	-1747.41	517.52
	24NP	-690.02	393.126	.497	-1822.49	442.44
	24P	-1773.83*	393.126	.000	-2906.29	-641.36
0P	0N	-711.23	393.126	.462	-1843.69	421.24
	0NP	955.28	393.126	.152	-177.18	2087.75
	24N	340.34	393.126	.954	-792.13	1472.80
	24NP	265.26	393.126	.985	-867.21	1397.72
	24P	-818.55	393.126	.301	-1951.01	313.92
24N	0N	-1051.57	393.126	.085	-2184.03	80.90
	0NP	614.94	393.126	.623	-517.52	1747.41
	0P	-340.34	393.126	.954	-1472.80	792.13
	24NP	-75.08	393.126	1.000	-1207.54	1057.39
	24P	-1158.88*	393.126	.042	-2291.35	-26.42
24NP	0N	-976.49	393.126	.134	-2108.95	155.98

	0NP	690.02	393.126	.497	-442.44	1822.49
	0P	-265.26	393.126	.985	-1397.72	867.21
	24N	75.08	393.126	1.000	-1057.39	1207.54
	24P	-1083.81	393.126	.069	-2216.27	48.66
24P	0N	107.32	393.126	1.000	-1025.15	1239.78
	0NP	1773.83*	393.126	.000	641.36	2906.29
	0P	818.55	393.126	.301	-313.92	1951.01
	24N	1158.88*	393.126	.042	26.42	2291.35
	24NP	1083.81	393.126	.069	-48.66	2216.27

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 3477325.977.

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

Homogeneous Subsets

Value

Tukey HSD^{a,b}

Group	N	Subset		
		1	2	3
0NP	45	850.05		
24N	45	1464.99	1464.99	
24NP	45	1540.07	1540.07	1540.07
0P	45	1805.33	1805.33	1805.33
0N	45		2516.56	2516.56
24P	45			2623.88
Sig.		.152	.085	.069

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 3477325.977.

a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 45.000.

b. Alpha = .05.

Profile Plots

